

Land Capability Classification - Assessment of Carrying Capacity and Utilization Intensity

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Land capability assessment is a coherent and orderly method of determining the ability of land to sustain a specific use and level of management, without causing significant long-term degradation. In this work, land capability classification method has been used in Kilde Awulaelo – Ethiopia to estimate different land capability classes. Different parameters related to topography, environmental conditions and soils have been obtained through remote sensing and GIS applications along with field surveys in order to achieve capability classes. The results showed that in the Kilde Awulaelo District, no land units have been categorized as class V and VIII. The total area of land that is suitable for rainfed, irrigated agriculture and open vegetation growth (I, II, III and IV) is around 67% of the study area. On the other hand, classes suitable for grazing or afforestation (VI and VII) represent less than 29% of the total area. In addition, the land utilization intensity map showed that the majority of the study area is properly utilized. The study demonstrated the capacity of the remote sensing and GIS applications in land capability assessment studies.

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